

Supporting Information for

Redox Cycling on Unmodified Gold Interdigitated Ultramicroelectrode Arrays for Interferent Free Electrochemical Detection of Pyocyanin

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7 1. Electrode Fabrication

8 Each sensor consisted of two combs of gold interdigitated ultramicroelectrodes, as working electrodes, as well
9 as platinum pseudo reference and platinum counter electrodes. Chips were designed with a peripheral microSD
10 pinout to permit interfacing with external electronics via a microSD port. All devices were fabricated on 4-inch
11 silicon wafers bearing a thermally grown 300 nm silicon dioxide layer. Blanket metal evaporation of Titanium
12 (10 nm) and Gold (100 nm) (Temescal FC-2000 E-beam evaporator) and lift-off techniques was employed to
13 define the gold ultramicro Interdigitated Electrode (IDEs). The first comb (WE₁) had 33 tines, while the second
14 comb two (WE₂) had 34 tines. Each comb was 1 μm wide, 187 μm long, 100 nm high and had an inter-electrode

15 gap of 2 μm . A second metal evaporation and subsequent lift-off step was undertaken to pattern platinum
16 interconnection tracks, contact pads, the counter electrode (300 μm x 7mm) and the pseudo reference electrode
17 (300 μm x 7mm). Silicon nitride was then blanket deposited using plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition
18 across the whole wafer to act as an insulating layer. This insulating layer was used to prevent unwanted
19 electrochemical interactions along the connection tracks. To allow electrolyte access to the ultramicroband
20 electrodes, vias (windows) were opened in the insulating Si_3N_4 layer (above the sensor electrodes using
21 photolithography and dry etching. Additional vias were opened over the counter and pseudo-reference
22 electrodes as well as the periphery microSD contact pads. Each device contained three separate interdigitated
23 electrode sensors which are separated by 1.88 mm. This separation was maintained to prevent cross talk, i.e.,
24 electrochemical reactions occurring at one sensor from interfering with a neighbouring sensor to prevent cross
25 talk. Following fabrication, the wafer was diced to produce 28 separate chip dice.

26 Following fabrication, each chip was inspected using optical microscopy to identify any visible defects or faults
27 and any defective chips discarded. Prior to electrochemical characterisation, chips were first cleaned by rinsing
28 with acetone followed by de-ionized water. The chips were subsequently dried using nitrogen and inserted into
29 an electrochemical holder. Electrochemical analysis was performed using an Autolab Bipotentiostat (MAC80150
30 with BA Module, Metrohm), within a Faraday cage. Cyclic voltammograms (CV) were performed in the voltage
31 range of -0.15 V to 0.45 V at 50 mV/s at the first interdigitated comb (WE_1) in 1 mM ferrocene carboxylic acid
32 (FCA, Sigma Aldrich, 97%) while the second interdigitated comb of electrodes, (WE_2) was biased at -0.15 V; for
33 the duration of the scans. All electrochemical measurements were recorded versus the on-chip platinum counter
34 and platinum pseudo-reference electrodes in solutions at room temperature ($\sim 21^\circ\text{C}$).

35 2. UV-Vis Measurements

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37 Figure S1 (a) shows the UV-Vis spectra obtained for various concentrations of pyocyanin, diluted from a stock
38 solution, which had been dissolved in chloroform, and acidified using 0.2M HCl.

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40 *Figure S1: UV-Vis spectra obtained for acidified solutions of various concentrations of pyocyanin.*41

3. Real Sample Analysis

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P. aeruginosa strains PA17, PA40, and PA41 were grown in 10 mL of TSB for 16 h at 37°C. In eight 250 mL conical flasks 49.5 mL NB and 1% (v/v) glycerol was added, two flasks were inoculated with 0.5 mL of the initial cultures per strain. The flasks were then incubated at 37°C with shaking at 180 rpm for a period of 72 h. After the first 72 h one flask was removed per strain and centrifuged at 5,000 x g for 10 min in the Beckman Coulter Avanti J-E, the cell pellet was separated from the supernatant and disposed of. The pyocyanin quantification method used during this assay is an adaptation of the method outlined by Abdelaziz et al. ¹ After the first 72 h one flask was removed per strain and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 30 min in the Beckman Coulter Avanti J-E, the cell pellet was separated from the supernatant and disposed of.

The remaining supernatant was then syringe filtered using 10 mL syringes (*BD Emerald, USA*) through 0.2 μm filters, light sensitive conditions were observed from this point forward. 10 mL of supernatant per strain was combined with 10 mL of chloroform and vortexed for 20 s and then centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 5 min. The lower chloroform layer containing pyocyanin was separated from the top layer, after which 10 mL of 0.2 M HCl was added to the chloroform then mixed by vortex for 20 s followed by centrifugation at 10,000 x g for 5 min. 1 mL

of the HCl containing the acidified pyocyanin was measured using the Pharmacia Biotech Novaspec II set to a wavelength of 520 nm, which was blanked with 1 mL of 0.2 M HCl. The resulting absorbance was then multiplied by 17.072 to obtain the concentration of pyocyanin in mg/L, in line with literature.^{2,3} This was then converted into μM and compared to the electrochemical sensor. The results for the electrochemical sensor are shown in Figure S2.

Sample	A ₅₂₀	mg/L	μM
PA41 72hr	0.234	3.99	19.00
PA40 72hr	0.274	4.68	22.25
PA17 72hr	0.224	3.82	18.19

43 Table S1: Various real-world samples of differing strains of *P. Aeruginosa*, with absorbance determined and subsequently
 44 pyocyanin concentration determined.

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47 Figure 2: LSVs for real samples of various strains of *P. aeruginosa* vs Pt reference electrode in nutrient broth. Each LSV
 48 represents 3 averaged scans for the oxidative current observed at WE2, when a bias of -0.4 V is employed.

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4. References

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